

Studies in Benzimidazo Thiazolo Quinoxalines and Benzimidazo Thiazino Quinoxalines

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Benzimidazo (2', 1' : 2, 3) thiazolo (4, 5-b) quinoxalines and 7H-benzimidazo (1', 2' : 4, 5) (1 : 4) thiazino (2, 3-b) quinoxalines have been synthesised by the condensations of 2-mercapto benzimidazoles with 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines and 2-(mercaptomethyl) benzimidazole with 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines respectively.

In continuation of our efforts to find new chemotherapeutics in quinoxalines fused with other heterocyclic ring systems^{1,2}, we report here two new heterocyclic ring systems i.e. benzimidazo (2', 1' : 2, 3) thiazolo (4, 5-b) quinoxalines I and 7H-benzimidazo (1', 2' : 4, 5) (1 : 4) thiazino (2, 3-b) quinoxalines II.

The synthesis of I has been achieved by the condensation of 2-mercapto benzimidazoles (III) with 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines (IV).

Similarly II has been synthesised by the condensation of 2-mercapto methyl benzimidazole (VI) with 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxaline (IV).

In the case of benzimidazoles mono substituted in the benzene nucleus the formation of more than one product through the reaction of either of the two nitrogens is possible. However in all the cases studied only one product was obtained*. This is in analogy with reports in literature where also rigorous assignment for substitution have not been made³. So in these products the group R₃ could be considered to be either at 9 or 10 position of I.

1. Simran Singh, R. S. Narang, Mohinder Singh and Harjit Singh, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 12.
2. Simran Singh, Sardul Singh and K. S. Narang, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 569.

* The homogeneity of the product checked through t.l.c. plates coated with silica gel G. were eluted with chloroform or ethylene dichloride and were developed with iodine after drying.

3. J. B. Wright, *Chem. Rev.*, 1951, **48**, 400.

In case of unsubstituted or symmetrically substituted dichloro quinoxalines both the halogens are equally labile. However different substituents affect the reactivity at C₁ and C₂ to different extent⁴. In case of 6-nitro-2 : 3-dichloro quinoxaline, the nitro group due to

its strong electron attracting power makes the chlorine atom at position 2 more mobile which subsequently reacts with thiol group of II giving the intermediate V ($R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$). Unlike the nitro group the methyl and chloro groups at position 6 of the 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxaline will deactivate the chlorine at position 2 and hence the chlorine at position 3 will react with the mercapto group of III giving the intermediate V ($R_1 = \text{CH}_3$ and Cl, $R_2 = \text{H}$). Subsequently V would furnish I ($R_1 = \text{H}$, $R_2 = \text{NO}_2$) and ($R_1 = \text{CH}_3$ and Cl and $R_2 = \text{H}$) respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *2-Mercapto benzimidazoles* : These were prepared from *o*-phenylene diamines^{5,6}.
2. *2 : 3-Dichloro quinoxalines* : These were prepared by treating *o*-phenylene diamines with diethyl oxalate and subsequently converting 2 : 3-dihydroxy quinoxalines to 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines with phosphorus pentachloride or phosphorus oxychloride⁷⁻¹⁰.
3. *Condensations of 2-mercapto benzimidazoles (III) with 2 : 3-dichloroquinoxalines (IV) or synthesis of benzimidazo (2', 1' : 2, 3) thiazolo (4,5-b) quinoxaline* : *General Procedure* : Equivalent amounts of 2-mercapto benzimidazoles and 2 : 3-dichloro quinoxalines were

4. R. D. Haworth and S. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 777.
5. J. A. V. Allan and B. D. Deacon, *Org. Synthesis*, 1950, 30, 56.
6. Lellmann, *Liebigs Annalen der Chemie*, 221, 9, c.f., *Beil*, 24, 119, 26.
7. M. A. Phillips, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2397.
8. O. Hinsberg and J. Pollak, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 784.
9. E. H. Uskerwood and M. A. Whitely, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 1069.
10. G. W. H. Cheeseman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1171.

heated together at 140–50° in an oil bath for 2 hrs. The solid was triturated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted 2-mercapto benzimidazole. It was collected, washed with water and crystallised from appropriate solvents (Table I).

TABLE I

S.No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	m.p. °C	Solvent of crystallisation	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analytical Results*	
								Found %	Reqd. %
1.	H	H	H	225	Dioxan	64	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₄ S	C, 64.70	65.21
								H, 3.30	2.89
								N, 19.89	20.29
2.	H	NO ₂	H	260	„	65	C ₁₅ H ₇ N ₆ SO ₂	N, 21.68	21.80
3.	Br	Br	H	285	„	60	C ₁₅ H ₆ Br ₂ N ₄ S	N, 12.59	12.90
4.	Cl	H	H	210	„	62	C ₁₅ H ₇ ClN ₄ S	N, 17.85	18.06
5.	CH ₃	H	H	230	Acetic acid	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	N, 19.72	19.31
6.	NO ₂	NO ₂	H	230	Dioxan/ethanol	60	C ₁₅ H ₆ N ₆ SO ₄	N, 22.70	22.95
								S, 8.44	8.74
7.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	188	Ethanol	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ S	N, 18.10	18.35
8.	H	H	CH ₃	180	Ethanol	63	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	N, 19.50	19.31
9.	H	NO ₂	CH ₃	200	Ethanol	58	C ₁₆ H ₉ N ₆ SO ₂	N, 20.95	20.89
10.	NO ₂	NO ₂	CH ₃	260	Ethanol	64	C ₁₆ H ₈ N ₆ SO ₄	S, 8.00	8.42
11.	Cl	H	CH ₃	140	„	53	C ₁₆ H ₉ ClN ₄ S	N, 16.96	17.28
12.	Br	Br	CH ₃	200	„	55	C ₁₆ H ₈ Br ₂ N ₄ S	N, 12.39	12.50
13.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	227	„	61	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ S	N, 18.15	18.42
14.	H	H	Cl	230	Acetic acid	55	C ₁₅ H ₇ ClN ₄ S	N, 18.45	18.06
15.	H	NO ₂	Cl	195	„	53	C ₁₆ H ₆ ClN ₆ SO ₂	N, 19.85	19.71
16.	CH ₃	H	Cl	170	„	52	C ₁₆ H ₉ ClN ₄ S	N, 16.78	17.28
17.	Cl	H	Cl	215	„	55	C ₁₅ H ₆ Cl ₂ N ₄ S	N, 16.32	16.23
18.	CH ₃	CH ₃	Cl	174	Ethanol	52	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ S	N, 16.20	16.37

* Analytical results are by M/s. B. N. Anand and L. K. Khullar, Microanalysts, Panjab University, Chemistry Department, Chandigarh.

4. *2-(Mercapto methyl) benzimidazole*: It was prepared by the condensation of thioacetic acid and *o*-phenylene diamine¹¹.

5. *Condensation of 2-(mercapto methyl) benzimidazole (VI) with 2:3-dichloro quinoxalines (IV) or synthesis of 7H-benzimidazo (1', 2': 4, 5) (1, 4) thiazino (2,3-b) quinoxaline (II): General Procedure*: Equivalent amounts of 2-(mercapto methyl) benzimidazole (VI) and 2:3-dichloro quinoxalines (IV) were heated together in an oil bath at 150–60° for 3 hrs. The solid was triturated with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution to remove unreacted 2-mercapto methyl benzimidazole. The products were crystallised from appropriate solvents (Table II).

S.No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Solvent of crystallisation	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analytical Results	
							Found %	Reqd. %
1.	H	H	240	Ethanol	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	C, 66.15	66.20
							H, 3.20	3.44
							N, 19.05	19.31
2.	CH ₃	H	212	„	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ S	N, 18.35	18.42
3.	Cl	H	220	„	56	C ₁₆ H ₉ ClN ₄ S	N, 16.96	17.28

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